

Components, Criteria and Levels of Forming the Economic Concepts of Preschool Children

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Abstract: In this article the issues of providing economic concepts to the young generation, awakening and motivating activity in economic processes, taking into account the unique psychological and pedagogical factors of children in the organization of educational activities are covered in detail.

Keywords: economic concept, psychological-pedagogical factor, pedagogical problem, education and training, alternative, pedagogical improvisation, component.

Introduction. In the context of the reforms in the field of education, the definition of new requirements for providing the young generation with economic concepts, forming a broad worldview and educating them spiritual and moral qualities shows the need to decide on an innovative approach to the organization of pedagogical activities. All this is proof that the President of our republic, Sh. Mirziyoyev, approved a number of documents related to the reform of the field of preschool education and upbringing in the next five years and put it into practice.

Comprehensive reforms in the education system of our country require the study, analysis of advanced foreign educational experience and the development of socio-pedagogical and didactic features of adaptation to the conditions of educational institutions. At the stage of the development of the current society, the transition from the "knowledgeable" educational approach to the competence-oriented educational system and the formation of personal characteristics of the economic knowledge expected to be acquired by preschool children are considered as one of the urgent pedagogical problems.¹

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Preschool Education and Training"², preschool education and training is to provide education and training to children, to develop them intellectually, morally, ethically, aesthetically and physically, as well as being recognized as a type of continuous education aimed at preparing children for general secondary education, today puts new tasks before the representatives of this field. In particular, in the State Standard³ of Preschool Education organization of the pre-school education system based on modern requirements, introduction of effective forms and methods of education of pre-school children

¹ <http://kompy.info/bolajak-oqituvchilarining-akt-boyicha-kasbiy-kompetentligini-s.html>

² Resolution of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 16, 2019 "On preschool education and training" No. ORQ-595 <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/4646908>

³ OResolution No. 802 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 22, 2020 "On Approval of the State Standard of Preschool Education and Training". <https://lex.uz/docs/5179335>

based on national, universal and spiritual values will be shown.

the state requirements for the development of primary and preschool children of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the "First Step"⁴ state curriculum, the role of economic concepts in the mental and spiritual development of 3-7-year-old children is incomparable. Economic concepts serve as a powerful and effective tool of intellectual, moral and aesthetic upbringing of children, which has a great impact on the intellectual development and enrichment of the child.

Research Methodology. Processes and experiences during preschool education are of special importance. There is a correlation between physical movement and cognitive development and cognitive development in preschool children. Children begin to develop not only motor skills, but also cognitive, social and emotional skills.

There are three interrelated educational cycles in introducing preschool children to economic concepts:

1. Stimulating and motivating economic processes.
2. To understand the changes taking place, to express the meaning of economic events with familiar or unfamiliar words, to explain-analysis-synthesis of usual or unusual economic events.
3. Expression of attitude to the object being studied in economic activity-reflection.

When organizing educational activities at the listed stages, pedagogues-educators must take into account the following specific psychological and pedagogical factors in children:

- ✓ interests are short-term;
- ✓ predominance of unstable and involuntary attention;
- ✓ superiority of visual-motor thinking, increased movement activity;
- ✓ desire to play;
- ✓ different levels of interest in learning.

Taking psychological and pedagogical factors into account, effective organization of educational activities, ensures that children have ideas about economic processes, the name and essence of economic events. This is the development of economic thinking in preschool children, formation of independent thinking, self-awareness skills, entrepreneurship, frugality, hard work, initiative by educating the sense of comradeship, friendship and community expands its possibilities. Professional skills and competence of pedagogues-educators occupy a special place in introducing children to economic concepts.

Modern pre-school education requires compliance with aesthetic requirements in the organization of children's life, formation of moral qualities in the pedagogical process, activity of the educator within the requirements of general cultural competence. Professional motivation is an important factor in achieving effectiveness in the teacher's pedagogical activities. The educator should raise the value of each activity in the context of professional motivation.

Motive improves pedagogical activity and directs to success. Motives appear at the stage of pedagogical activity and self-analysis. Motives create different forms of pedagogical activity. Only then, the scope of the goal set by him for training will be aligned with the content of the social order. The correct selection of the goal motivates the methodical and effective organization of training. It is one of the important conditions that every method and means used during the training should be aimed at ensuring the achievement of the intended goal. Due to the instability of children of preschool age, there is a need for alternative forms of methods and

⁴ The first step" is the state curriculum of the preschool education organization. Tashkent. 2022 <https://www.unicef.org/uzbekistan/media/3771/file/>

tools chosen by the educator. This situation creates an atmosphere of pedagogical improvisation.

Alternative (French alternative; Latin alter - one of two) - 1) two or more possible decisions, the path taken, the desired options and one of the other the need to choose.⁵

Pedagogical improvisation is a process that is not planned in advance, based on educational tasks, and is quickly implemented in the process of pedagogical communication. In addition, the professional competences of educators, in particular, the competences related to the organization of the process of introduction to economic knowledge, were also analyzed by observing the training.

Educators have insufficient knowledge and experience of economic education technologies and their skills in organizing a multifunctional approach in training, limited opportunities to use information technologies (low information literacy, lack of material equipment, computers, projectors, electronic boards) and most traditional it was determined that they used the methods. One of the methodological obstacles is the fact that educators are not fully provided with educational and methodological resources for introducing preschool children to economic concepts.⁶ Economic concepts and economic relations are first of all brought up in the family from early childhood. Family members and adults need to introduce children to economic relationships every day and ensure that they communicate through economic concepts. The influence of the family in preparing children for school education is significant. Therefore, the development of methodical advice for parents was selected as a separate plan in the formative phase of the research. Based on our observations, organizational-pedagogical problems, which are evident when providing information about economic concepts to preschool children, confirmed that the state order on children's readiness for school education is insufficiently fulfilled. Within the framework of the research, the current situation was studied, and the directions of the next phase of experimental work were determined. They are as follows:

- to determine the optimal ways of introducing preschool children to economic concepts;
- improvement of the mechanism of the process of familiarizing preschoolers with economic concepts;
- identification of effective technologies that serve to develop children's ideas about economic concepts;
- systematization of methods and technologies;
- to identify effective ways and means of developing children's knowledge, skills, skills and competencies about economic concepts by means of innovative and multifunctional approaches, and to develop methodical guidelines for their implementation.

Above, by studying and analyzing the opinions of great writers on economy and economic education, it was possible to determine the components of improving the economic concepts of preschool children.

Given the trust and responsibility of teachers, it is important to first develop the professional competence of future educators, to study the disciplines in depth and to form them methodologically in line with modern requirements.⁷

Analysis and results. Development of economic concepts of preschool children requires clarification of the components of this process. It is desirable to clarify the components and

⁵ <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Alternativa>

⁶ Quchqorova N.M. Technologies of methodological improvement of economic competence of future educators. p.f.d. (DSc) autoref. Namangan–2023., P-17.

⁷ Quchqorova N.M. Components and criteria of economic culture of future teachers. E3S Web of Conferences 402, 08003 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202340208003> TransSiberia 2023 Urgench State University, Urgench, Uzbekistan

indicators of the development of children's economic concepts in the preschool educational organization. Based on this basis, the following components of the development of economic concepts of preschool children were identified (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Formation of economic concepts of preschool children components

The motivational component is determined by the understanding of the content and importance of economic activities, their legal aspects, and their interrelationship with the spiritual and moral foundations of economic development in the educational processes of preschool children in MTT.

Intellectual component - economic thinking of preschool children and understanding of their intellectual level and personal capabilities. It is determined by the level of possession of sufficient economic concepts to understand and reason about the facts, concepts, ideas in the economic relations of society, the state, MTT and the family.

Riskological competence - individual characteristics such as hard work, thrift, entrepreneurship, business acumen, manifested as a result of taking risks in economic activities of preschool children.

The economic activity - oriented component implies acquiring practical skills in solving economic issues related to life and professional activity.

Based on the components shown in Figure 1, three groups of criteria for the development of economic concepts of preschool children were defined: cognitive ; motivational; creative-active. Based on these criteria, indicators corresponding to three (high, medium and low) levels were determined:

High level: preschool children can explain the basic meaning of economic concepts, show a clear and stable interest in their parents' work, have an understanding of their parents' profession, use economic words and phrases; they can apply the concepts learned in the games in life; they are ready to communicate with adults and peers, ask many questions and try to find answers to them independently; able to help adults and peers at work, consciously deal with the implementation of labor activities, carefully treat work topics, its results, complete the work started, able to correctly evaluate the results of one's own work and the results of colleagues ; rational use of materials; actively supports and develops creative researches of businessmen, talented, inventive, peers in the process of effective activity ; seeks and knows how to take the initiative, performs tasks with determination, brings the started work to the end.

Intermediate level: children have ideas about economic concepts, but cannot always explain them; they have an unstable interest in the needs of the family, in the work of their parents; the concepts they have are not clear, vague, superficial; children ask questions about the events around them only after the educator increases their interest in knowledge through game

conditions, exercises, creative tasks, they have enough ideas about the world around them, but do not know how to use the concepts available in the game; organizing one's activities under the guidance of adults, completing tasks on time; loyal to material values, they are strong, proactive, know how to approach work creatively, but the assigned work is carried out conscientiously, only under the guidance of adults; they are not always active, they can partially show persistence in achieving the goal.

At a low level: children cannot explain the meaning of economic concepts, do not show interest in family needs, parents' work, events surrounding modern society, do not use economic words in speech; not interested in effective activities, acting only as external observers; they do not bring the work to the end, do not know how to negotiate during the implementation of joint labor activities, quickly lose interest in work and leave their work and return to the game; do not tend to be careful with personal and social property; when doing work, they do not show any interest in their results; irresponsible, self-initiative, does not show perseverance in achieving the goal.

The views of scientists on the general development of preschool children, their education and the development of their imagination about economic concepts, national and foreign experiences made it possible to form the following conclusions: Historical foundations of the formation of economic concepts in preschool children and analysis of scientific research works " economic imagination ", "economic understanding", "economic education", "economic activity", "polyfunctional", "polyfunctional approach" The meaning of such concepts was explained.

3. The content of activities related to the structural structure of preschool children's economic concepts (economic imagination, economic education, economic upbringing, economic activity) and the mutual harmony of the competences of the support and development spheres related to the content were determined on the basis of strict determination. it was possible to determine the components of forming the economic concepts of preschool children. In the organization of preschool education, the following components for the formation of children's economic concepts were determined: motivational, intellectual, riskological, oriented to economic activity.

5. As a result of the study of the practical situation of the problem of the formation of economic concepts of preschool children, the influence of parents and educators was studied on the basis of a questionnaire survey and interviews, and economic concepts and economic relations, first of all, MTT and upbringing in the family from early childhood, family members and the need for adults to daily introduce children to economic relations and ensure that they communicate through economic concepts has been confirmed. Pedagogical, psychological, and methodical problems that are evident when providing information about economic concepts to preschool children confirmed that the state order on children's readiness for school education is not sufficiently fulfilled.

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